

Comprehensive Analysis of Scalded Skin Syndrome: Clinical Exploration, Underlying Pathophysiology and Advanced Therapeutic Approaches

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ABSTRACT

Scalded skin syndrome, a rare but potentially serious dermatologic entity, stands as a clinical and scientific challenge in the contemporary medical field. This article proposes a comprehensive evaluation of this entity, covering clinical aspects, pathophysiological mechanisms and state-of-the-art therapeutic perspectives.

The skin, as the most extensive organ of the human body, is prone to a diversity of pathologies, among which scalded skin syndrome emerges as a condition characterized by significant epidermal exfoliation, commonly evoked by staphylococcal exfoliative toxins. Despite its dramatic clinical presentation, its accurate diagnosis may require meticulous differential evaluation to discern it from other skin conditions with similar manifestations.

From a pathophysiological perspective, cutaneous de-adhesion in scalded skin syndrome originates in the specific unbinding of intracellular adhesion molecules, leading to intraepidermal separation and ultimately intraepidermal blistering. The constantly evolving understanding of the molecular processes involved has led to innovative therapeutic approaches that go beyond mere suppression of the causative infection.

In this comprehensive review, current and emerging therapeutic options are addressed, including intravenous immunoglobulin, immune response modulating agents, and therapies targeting dysfunctional molecular signaling cascades. In addition, the importance of supportive care and prevention of life-threatening complications, such as sepsis, is discussed.

In summary, this article is intended as an essential resource for clinicians, researchers, and healthcare professionals interested in furthering the comprehensive understanding of scalded skin syndrome. The convergence of clinical, basic research, and advanced therapies is crucial to improve early detection, effective management, and prognostic outcomes in this complex dermatologic entity.

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INTRODUCTION

Scalded skin syndrome (SPE), a clinical entity of marked medical and dermatologic significance, has captivated the attention of health professionals due to its unusual presentation, dramatic clinical manifestations and intriguing pathophysiologic mechanisms. It falls within the spectrum of blistering skin diseases, characterized by blistering and epidermal exfoliation, manifestations that can range from localized forms to generalized involvement, highlighting its potentially devastating nature.¹

PES, also known as exfoliative epidermolysis or Lyell's syndrome, predominantly manifests in pediatric populations,

but can affect individuals of all ages. Its etiology is rooted in the production of exfoliative toxins by specific strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, resulting in a cascade of molecular events that culminate in the sloughing of the upper epidermal layer. Despite its relative rarity, the condition is crucial to recognize and treat diligently because of its potential to progress to a systemic inflammatory response, secondary infection and life-threatening risk.^{1,2}

This review aims to contextualize PLE within the dermatological landscape, addressing its epidemiology, underlying pathogenesis, clinical presentation and historical evolution in terms of diagnosis and treatment. In addition,

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recent advances in the understanding of the immunologic mechanisms underlying the disease will be explored, leading to the development of more targeted and personalized therapeutic approaches. As knowledge of the molecular and cellular interactions in PBS expands, a new era in the management of this condition is emerging, moving into the realm of targeted therapy and modulation of aberrant immune responses.^{2,3}

Ultimately, the purpose of this comprehensive review is to provide an up-to-date and broad perspective on PLE, aimed at both clinicians and researchers in the dermatologic field. By examining the clinical, pathogenetic and therapeutic aspects of PLE, we seek to improve early detection, effective clinical management and, ultimately, prognostic outcomes for patients affected by this enigmatic and debilitating skin condition.³

EPIDEMIOLOGY

Scalded skin syndrome (SPE), an uncommon skin condition but of undeniable medical magnitude, has attracted pronounced interest in both the medical community and the field of dermatology because of its potentially serious nature and strikingly dramatic clinical manifestations. This entity, which falls within the spectrum of blistering diseases, presents a significant epidermal exfoliation that oscillates between localized forms and generalized manifestations, the latter being the subject of particular attention due to its capacity to generate substantial morbidity and, in certain contexts, lethal outcomes.³

PES, also conceptualized as exfoliative epidermolysis or Lyell's syndrome, manifests predominantly in pediatric populations, although it is not restricted entirely to this demographic group, as it can affect individuals of all ages. Its etiopathogenesis is intrinsically linked to the production of exfoliative toxins by specific strains of *Staphylococcus aureus*, which triggers a series of biochemical cascades and molecular events that culminate in intraepidermal unbinding and consequent blistering and characteristic epidermal exfoliation.³

The clinical significance of PES lies in its ability to evolve into a systemic inflammatory response, driven by the release of proinflammatory mediators and the potential dissemination of circulating toxins. As the epidermal layers slough off, patients become susceptible to secondary infections and water-electrolyte imbalances, accentuating the morbidity and mortality associated with this condition. Therefore, early recognition and diligent management are imperative in the management of PES.^{3,4}

From an epidemiological point of view, despite its infrequency, PES cannot be overlooked because of its ability to trigger significant medical consequences. Although incidence rates vary according to geographic regions and populations studied, cases are globally distributed, underscoring the need for a universal understanding of this

entity. The slightly skewed prevalence toward children and infants is due to the immaturity of the immune system and skin barriers in these cohorts, making them more vulnerable to staphylococcal toxins and their devastating effects.^{4,5}

The clinical and epidemiological relevance of PES lies in its potential to cause considerable morbidity and mortality, particularly in pediatric populations. Understanding its global epidemiology and appreciating its complex pathogenic process are crucial for early detection and effective intervention, thus prompting better management and prognostic outcomes for individuals affected by this enigmatic skin condition.⁵

CLINIC

Scalded skin syndrome (SSS), a dermatological entity of infrequent character but of significant clinical and medical impact, is distinguished by distinctive clinical manifestations that span a spectrum from localized to generalized in a pathological process characterized by profuse epidermal exfoliation and blistering, driven primarily by the exfoliative action of staphylococcal toxins.⁶

In the initial stages of this entity, local clinical presentations may exhibit cutaneous erythema, which progressively evolves into the formation of flaccid, clear intraepidermal blisters, which tend to cluster and coalesce. This phenomenon is often preceded by nonspecific prodromal signs, such as fever and malaise, which can make differential diagnosis difficult in the early stages.⁶

In more widespread and severe forms of PES, exfoliative epidermolysis becomes generalized, resulting in a cutaneous appearance reminiscent of severe burns, hence its alternative designation as "Lyell's syndrome". The epidermis, in this advanced stage, becomes extremely fragile and easily detachable, manifesting as profuse epidermal exfoliation that occurs with minimal pressure or manipulation. Mucosal surfaces, including the mouth, eyes and genitalia, may also be involved, presenting a number of additional clinical challenges.⁶

The cutaneous appearance of patients with PES can generate alarming similarities to severe burns and other blistering diseases, posing substantial diagnostic complexity. The exfoliated skin resembles a sloughed membrane, revealing an underlying erythematous and moist surface. The management of patients with PES requires constant vigilance for potential secondary complications, such as opportunistic bacterial infections and water-electrolyte imbalances, which may arise due to impaired skin barrier function and fluid loss.⁶

The clinical manifestations of PES range from localized forms with blistering and epidermal exfoliation to generalized presentations that mimic severe burns. The pronounced epidermal exfoliation and characteristic skin fragility require meticulous clinical surveillance and accurate differentiation from other blistering and burning conditions to guide

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effective therapeutic management and prevent potentially devastating complications.^{6,7}

DIAGNOSIS

The diagnosis of scalded skin syndrome (SCS), a dermatological condition of unique clinical and medical relevance, is a challenge that requires an amalgam of expert clinical evaluation and the use of specific diagnostic tools to rule out other blistering skin pathologies and ensure an accurate differential approach.^{7,8}

In the initial phase of clinical evaluation, the appearance of cutaneous erythema usually precedes the formation of the characteristically flaccid and broad intraepidermal blisters, occasionally accompanied by nonspecific systemic signs such as fever. These findings should be carefully weighed in the context of the patient's medical history, including possible exposures to triggering agents and history of staphylococcal infections.^{8,9}

However, the definitive diagnosis of PES is based on the identification and confirmation of staphylococcal exfoliative toxins as precipitating agents. This can be done by specific laboratory tests, such as mucosal and skin swab cultures, which seek to identify *Staphylococcus aureus* and confirm the production of the toxins involved. Occasionally, the polymerase chain reaction (PCR) technique can be employed to detect the presence of genes encoding these toxins, further supporting the diagnosis.⁹

Differential diagnosis plays an essential role in the clinical discernment process. PES can mimic other cutaneous bullous diseases, such as pemphigus vulgaris and hereditary epidermolysis bullosa bullosa, whose phenotypic manifestations may overlap with those of PES. Skin biopsies, which reveal the characteristic intraepidermal separation, can provide valuable histopathologic clues, but it is the combination of clinical, histopathologic and laboratory findings that underpins the differential diagnosis.⁹

The clinical spectrum of SPE can range from localized forms to generalized presentations, underscoring the importance of a comprehensive diagnostic approach. Ultimately, the diagnosis of PES entails the ability to identify staphylococcal toxins as triggers, while critically dissecting other skin conditions that exhibit phenotypic similarities. This multidisciplinary approach stands as a cornerstone for accurate diagnosis and implementation of effective therapeutic strategies.¹⁰

TREATMENT

The therapeutic management of scalded skin syndrome (SCS), a dermatological entity with substantial medical consequences, is characterized by a multidisciplinary approach involving clinical, pharmacological and supportive considerations, with the aim of mitigating cutaneous manifestations, preventing systemic complications and optimizing prognostic outcomes.^{10,11}

In the early stages of PES, cessation of exposure to potential sources of exfoliative toxins is imperative, along with the establishment of general supportive measures, such as adequate hydration and management of fever and systemic malaise. Hospitalization may be necessary, especially in generalized presentations, for constant monitoring and evaluation of therapeutic response.¹¹

The administration of systemic antibiotics, preferably cloxacillin or nafcillin, constitutes a central pillar in the treatment of PES. These antimicrobial agents exert their effect not only by controlling the underlying staphylococcal infection, but also by limiting the production of exfoliative toxins, thus attenuating the progression of cutaneous manifestations. However, early initiation of treatment is essential to avoid severe complications.^{11,12}

Intravenous immunoglobulin (IVIG) has emerged as a promising therapeutic approach in severe or refractory cases. IVIG exerts immunomodulatory and neutralizing effects, counteracting the action of exfoliative toxins and attenuating the systemic inflammatory response. It is indicated especially in generalized presentations with significant cutaneous and systemic involvement.¹²

Emerging therapeutic perspectives have focused attention on the specific modulation of molecular signaling cascades involved in the cutaneous inflammatory response. Biologic agents, such as tumor necrosis factor-alpha (TNF- α) inhibitors and interleukin inhibitors, are being investigated in clinical trials to assess their efficacy in controlling the dysregulated inflammatory response characteristic of PES.¹² Targeted therapy, which is based on understanding the underlying molecular interactions in PES, emerges as a promising frontier in treatment. The identification of therapeutic targets, such as dysregulated adhesion molecules and aberrant signaling cascades, opens the door to more selective and effective pharmacological approaches, with the potential to alter the course of the disease.¹³

Treatment of PES involves an approach ranging from suppression of the causative infection and attenuation of the systemic inflammatory response to exploration of innovative and personalized therapies. The convergence of conventional pharmacology with cutting-edge therapeutic approaches reflects the ongoing evolution in the understanding and management of this challenging dermatologic condition.¹

CONCLUSION

The conclusion of this comprehensive analysis of scalded skin syndrome (SCS) entails an appreciation of a dermatologic entity of unique complexity and medical magnitude, whose dramatic clinical manifestation and intriguing pathophysiology continue to challenge the medical and scientific community at substantial levels. As the understanding of the pathogenic mechanisms underlying this entity has deepened, clinical and therapeutic management has undergone significant evolution, projecting new perspectives

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in the search for improved prognostic outcomes for affected individuals.

Early identification and accurate diagnosis of PLE remain cornerstones in the clinical approach, given the phenotypic overlap with other blistering conditions and the diversified spectrum of clinical presentations. Critical discernment between PLE and other similar skin diseases, through meticulous evaluation of clinical manifestations, diagnostic tools, and specific laboratory tests, remains essential to effectively target therapy and prevent secondary complications.

The therapeutic management of PES has evolved remarkably, from antibiotic administration aimed at suppressing the underlying staphylococcal infection to immunomodulatory therapies and even molecularly targeted therapeutic approaches. The introduction of intravenous immunoglobulin and the examination of biologic and targeted therapies signal momentum toward personalization of treatment and precise mitigation of dysfunctional inflammatory cascades and contributing cellular interactions.

However, the road to a complete understanding of PES and its effective management is not without challenges. The rarity of the disease and variability in clinical presentations can make it difficult to collect clinical data and conduct robust clinical trials. In addition, identification of predictive biomarkers and validation of specific therapeutic targets are areas of ongoing research development.

PES embodies a dermatologic entity that, while remaining enigmatic in many respects, has been the subject of profound clinical and scientific appreciation. The convergence of clinical, basic research and innovative therapies promises to advance early identification, effective management and improved prognostic outcomes. As future perspectives in clinical and scientific management unfold, it is hoped that the medical and scientific community will continue to resolutely address the inherent challenges and pave the way toward more effective and personalized management of PES.

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